

THE CONCEPTS OF PROFESSIONAL FADE, CAUSES OF ORIGIN, COMPONENTS AND STAGES

Botirova Dilafruz Bozorovna

Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

"Pedagogy and psychology"

senior lecturer at the Department

botirovadilafruz300@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071221>

Abstract: This article focused on the mechanisms of a person's activity and interest in professional activities, while also focusing on how it can help individuals in this situation.

Key words: professional fading, professional boredom, professional identity, professional self, professional competence, professional cooperation.

Optimistic and cheerful people who are able to successfully overcome life difficulties and age-related crises "burn out" less often; those who occupy an active life position and resort to creative search when faced with difficult situations, have mental self-control, take care of replenishing their psychoenergetic and socio-psychological resources. Strong social, professional support, a reliable circle of friends, and Family Support reduce the risk of fading.

Mental fatigue (burnout) is understood as a set of special mental problems that occur in a person in connection with his professional activity. They were first introduced by H.J. While working as a psychiatrist at one of the health centers in 1974, Freudenberg observed the gradual emotional fading of many workers, loss of motivation and performance, and changes in health and the intellectual field. These were specialists in auxiliary professions - people who worked with full dedication and great enthusiasm in public organizations. After several months of such voluntary activity, these people showed a number of characteristic symptoms: fatigue, irritability, cynicism, etc., H.J. Freudenberg, unlike initial "emotional burning", is called "emotional burning".

Currently, in various domestic and Foreign Studies, the phenomenon of "mental fading" has a different meaning (emotional fading, occupational fading, occupational fading syndrome, etc.), but there is a similarity of interpretations with a careful analysis of these definitions. According to modern data, "mental fading" is understood as a state of physical, emotional and mental fading that manifests itself in the professions of the social sphere. R. Kotsiunas describes "appetite syndrome" as "a complex psychophysiological phenomenon accompanied by emotional, mental and physical fatigue due to prolonged emotional stress" [1].

The theoretical, practical, methodological approach to the professional training of educators, as well as the improvement of the conditions and methods of special training, the determination of professional knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the success of educators and the ability to work independently are the main problems of our time. Therefore, it is important to identify the socio-psychological aspects of successful upbringing. The introduction of new methods of psychodiagnostics, the enhancement of which consists in the development of Science, the activity of students and young people in the development of advanced innovations, the development of their mechanisms that serve to increase their intellectual potential.

There is a person who realizes his identity in society that it is quite natural that he is engaged in some type of activity that his interests touch the members of this society. From the proverb that the profession of our people will not be bad, we can point out that many examples from our history can be given about those who have gained the attention of the people through their profession. Among the individuals who are acting as skilled masters of their profession, boredom of their profession and cooling off of their profession have attracted many representatives of Social Sciences in recent times. In the direction of one of the main branches of general psychology, labor psychology, research is carried out in different directions, with a special emphasis on the process of fading an individual's passion for his activities. [1]

The slackening or “fading” of the passion that arises in a person in relation to his professional activity is known in the psychological literature of zhaxon as the “burnout” state, and in Uzbek it means “fading”. Currently, there is no single point of view on professional fading and the essence of its structure in the disciplines analyzing the activity of the individual. Relying on the latest data, “psychic burnout” is understood as a state of retardation in the acquisition of psycho-physiological, emotional and new technologies, which are observed in the professions of emotional state. [1]

Based on the research of Social Psychology, representatives of the following areas are considered to be relevant to the “risk” group on the process of professional fading: educators, psychologists, educators, doctors, people who often go on business trips, representatives of the service sector in a social and cultural direction, as well as bank employees. [2] leadership in this risk group belongs to educators and psychologists, and as a result of their dissatisfaction with their activities in addition to excessive mental activity, negative approaches to their professional activities arise as follows:

- high emotional approach to its activities;
- the feeling of not being able to find a place in the team;
- the need for regular activity, insufficient rest;
- negative social conditions and psychological state in the workplace;
- the abundance of day-long downloads;
- limited time for a delayed result;
- inability to control individual emotional state;
- the presence of an unsuitable result for the Labor spent;
- lack of skills for colleagues, administration, choosing the right communication path in difficult situations;
- improper management of the organization of pedagogical activities: loading, lesson schedule, lack of spiritual and material support;
- excess data;
- repeated controls and inspections.

It is natural that the predominance of the above factors affects the fact that an individual is tired or bored of his activities, falls into the state of stress. [3] in this case, aksari experts are increasingly prone to conflict situations. In order to establish a clear and successful psychological counseling by diagnosing the cause of such cases, attention should be paid to the main factors of learning to move away from professional fading and professional proportionality. These are:

- Not to introduce new ideas in the improvement of knowledge giving.
- Failure to introduce blind technologies into pedagogical activity.
- Assessment of the proportionality of an individual in relation to his profession.
- Analysis of the impact of the psychological climate of the team on the educational process.
- Opening the hidden possibilities of the personality of the educator.
- Improving the effectiveness of students ' knowledge by studying the psychological foundations of each pedagogical competence.
- Low Organization of open lessons and the absence of psychological analysis in it.

Below we have found it necessary to dwell on the two olmils calculated from the main factors of professional fading. It is at the last time that the following two reasons are more common in young specialists are noted. For this reason, experienced professionals will have to give the right advice in the field, which comes from their experience. [4]

1. The main reasons for professional fading and distance from professional proportionality:

Individual causes:

- A) a break from working on oneself;
- B) failure to acquire new knowledge of science;
- C) sticking to a constant uniform methodical style;
- D) dissatisfaction with one's activities;
- E) put a building on himself and ignore others;
- F) dissatisfaction with material interest;
- G) not attending classes of colleagues.

2. Socio-psychological factors:

- A) stay out of the attention of those around you;
- B) stay out of control of those around you;
- C) not being stimulated in accordance with activity;
- D) distance from professionals in their field;
- E) frequent mention of its shortcomings by the leadership.

Experienced colleagues and a psychologist specialist, who have noticed professional fading or a departure from the profession in young specialists, it is advisable to focus on the following. [4] to prevent professional fading in pedagogical activity, the following can be recommended:

- 1. Improve the skills of a regular educator.
- 2. Evaluate your personality through regular psychological tests.
- 3. Organization of various training, round tables and psychological consultations.
- 4. Organization of seminars in the field of science.
- 5. Conducting psychological seminars in the direction of analysis and synthesis and generalization of pedagogical activity.
- 6. Teaching methods for assessing the professional characteristics of a person by himself.
- 7. Arming with modern psychological techniques.

To eliminate it in the event of professional fading in a person, the pedagogical team can jointly maintain a specialist in its ranks by organizing their activities in harmony according to a clear plan. In the successful implementation of this activity, the actions of the psychologist sa'i deserve special attention. Elimination of professional fading in pedagogical activity: [5]

- 1. Organization of individual psychological training and conversations with the individual.

2. Organization of educational seminars to introduce innovations in the field of science.
3. Develop a recommendation by studying the capabilities of the individual.
4. Identification of cases of stress, depression that have occurred in pedagogical activity and the development of individual psychological counseling.
5. Analysis of the psychological climate of the team and the development of recommendations.

In social activity, it is natural that professional fading, which can occur with each individual, goes away at a certain interval of time. Help can be provided by providing him with positive guidance. Therefore, a practicing psychologist operating in the pedagogical sphere should not leave a single educator in the pedagogical community out of his control.

Library:

1. Аболин Л. М. Психологические механизмы эмоциональной устойчивости человека. Казань: КГУ., 1987. – 221 с.
2. Абрамов В.А. Исследование синдрома эмоционального выгорания на этапе мета обзоров. Ч. 1 / В.А. Абрамов, И.С. Алексейчук, А.И. Алексейчук // Журнал психиатрии и медицинской психологи. – 2008. – № 1 (18). – С. 117-123.
3. Багадаева О.Ю. / Мотивация персонала как организационное условие снижения профессионального стресса педагогов ДОО / Современное дошкольное образование. Теория и практика. 2016 №2. – 12-16 с.
4. Botirova D.B. Social-psychological foundations of the process of professional fading in pedagogic activities //Journal of Education and Innovation Research - 2023. – Т. 2. – No. 3.
5. Maklakov A.G. General psychology. Tutorial. SPb: Peter 2003
6. Psychology. Textbook. Ed. Rogova E.I. Vlados 2005

